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Iodine-catalyzed tandem oxidative coupling reaction: A one-pot strategy for the synthesis of new coumarin-fused pyrroles

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Abstract

The simple and facile strategy for the synthesis of 2,3-disubstituted-chromeno[4,3-b]pyrrole-4(1H)-ones has been established. This method describes the Kornblum oxidation reaction of acetophenones, followed by the Knoevenagel treatment of the resulted (het)arylglyoxals with active methylene compounds and consequently iodine-activated Michael type reaction with 4-amino coumarin in a one-pot manner to afford disubstituted chromeno[4,3-b]pyrrole-4(1H)-one derivatives.

Keywords: 2,3-Disubstituted chromeno[4,3-b]pyrrole-4(1H)-ones, Kornblum oxidation reaction, Iodine, Michael type reaction